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DELIVERABLE REPORT

Transnational Access to material testing facilities

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ABSTRACT

In this report, the activities of WP10 and transnational access to material testing facilities offered by the ARIES project are summarised. The report includes descriptions of HiRadMat and M-Branch infrastructures and description of the procedure for user selection. Provided transnational access and highlights of the results are cited in detail.

The estimated quantity of access units to be provided was 664 for HiRadMat and 768 for M-Branch. The overall quantity of access units that was provided throughout the duration of the project far exceeded the expectations, reaching 2426 for HiRadMat and 944 for M-Branch.

ARIES Consortium, 2022

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Delivery Slip

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. DESCRIPTION OF INFRASTRUCTURE.....	4
1.1. HiRADMAT	4
1.2. M-BRANCH.....	4
1.3. DESCRIPTION OF THE SELECTION PROCEDURE.....	5
2. SUMMARY OF TA PROVIDED.....	5
3. HIGHLIGHTS OF TA RESULTS	8
3.1. HiRADMAT	8
3.1. UNILAC M-BRANCH	10
4. LIST OF PUBLICATIONS.....	14
4.1. HiRADMAT	14
ANNEX: GLOSSARY.....	19

Executive summary

The material testing facilities under WP10 are HiRadMat and M-Branch. At HiRadMat (CERN, Switzerland) high-intensity pulsed beams are provided to irradiate material samples and accelerator components. Testing with both proton and ion beams is provided. At GSI Helmholtz Centre for Heavy Ion Research (Darmstadt, Germany), the UNILAC M-Branch facilities provide ion beams of all elements (from protons up to uranium). HiRadMat has offered a total of 2426 access units, while M-Branch delivered a total of 944 access units. After a recalculation of the distribution of Access units among the ARIES facilities, the total of access units of HiRadMat went from 200 to 664 and from 480 to 768 for UNILAC M-Branch. Thus, both facilities have exceeded the original expectations of the program.

1. Description of infrastructure

1.1. HiRADMAT

HiRadMat (High-Radiation to Materials) is a user facility that provides high-intensity pulsed beams to an irradiation area where material samples as well as accelerator component assemblies can be tested. HiRadMat uses the extracted beam from the CERN-SPS (Super Proton Synchrotron) with up to a few 10^{13} protons/pulse to a momentum of 440 GeV/c. The fast (single turn) extracted beam is transported into the HiRadMat experimental area where the test setup of materials is being installed. The beam spot size at the focal point at the experiment can vary from 0.25 to 2 mm² to offer sufficient flexibility to test materials at different deposited energy densities. The facility can also provide heavy ion beams like Pb⁸²⁺ with a beam energy of 177.4 GeV/nucleon (36.9 TeV per ion) resulting in a pulse energy of up to 21 kJ. HiRadMat as a dedicated facility for material and component testing with LHC type particle beam parameters is unique today. HiRadMat is serving the high-power targetry and accelerator physics community since 2011.

1.2. M-BRANCH

GSI operates a worldwide unique large-scale accelerator facility for swift heavy ions in the MeV to GeV energy regime. Irradiation sites for materials research accessible via the TA are located at the M-Branch providing ion beams between 3.4 and 11.4 MeV/nucleon from the UNILAC linear accelerator. The M-Branch houses three beamlines equipped with various in-situ and on-line techniques for material analysis without dismounting and exposing samples to air. The M1-beamline provides high-resolution scanning electron microscopy (HRSEM) to monitor beam-induced surface changes, as well as an ultra-high vacuum (UHV) irradiation chamber with atomic force and scanning tunneling microscopes (AFM/STM) for in-situ characterization of surface irradiation effects along with a Time-of-Flight Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry (ToF SIMS). The M2-beamline includes a four-circle X-ray diffractometer (XRD) to monitor crystallographic and structural beam-induced changes as a function of irradiation parameters (fluence, flux, etc.), while the M3-beamline has multi-

purpose chambers with a heating and cooling stage allowing sample irradiations at a temperature between 20 and 1,000 K and under various gas atmospheres. Absorption spectroscopy (FTIR, UV/Vis, and Raman) and thermal imaging by a fast IR camera is also possible in the M3 line.

1.3. DESCRIPTION OF THE SELECTION PROCEDURE

WP10 has two separate User Selection Panels, one per facility. To facilitate communication, to avoid duplication of experiments, and to direct experiments towards the most appropriate facility, each of the two USPs includes a representative from the other facility. The panels convene in regular intervals.

2. Summary of TA provided

Table 1 and Table 2 show an overview of the TA provided to HiRadMat and UNILAC M-Branch over the ARIES project duration. A total of 2426 access units to 41 users has been provided by HiRadMat and 944 access units to 33 users by UNILAC M-Branch respectively.

Facility	No. of projects			Total P1+ P2+ P3	Total no. of projects Annex 1 (amended numbers)	No. of users			Total P1+ P2+ P3	Total no. of users Annex 1 (amended numbers)	No. of access units			Total P1+ P2+ P3	Total no. of access units Annex 1 (amended numbers)
	P1	P2	P3			P1	P2	P3			P1	P2	P3		
HiRadMat	6	1	5	12	7	29	0	12	41	39	1328	328	770	2426	664
UNILAC	2	2	0	4	6	21	12	0	33	50	104	408	432	944	768

Table 1: List of TA projects at the HiRadMat facility.

TA Project Acronym	Experiment	No. of Users	Access Units	No. of Institutes	No. of Countries
ARIES-HiRadMat-2017-01	HRMT19 – BLM2	3	480	1	1

ARIES-HiRadMat-2017-02	HRMT21 – RotCol	2	88	2	2
ARIES-HiRadMat-2017-03	HRMT41 – ATLASPixel HRMT47 – ATLASPixRad	3	88	1	1
ARIES-HiRadMat-2017-04	HRMT38 – FlexMat	10	296	2	2
ARIES-HiRadMat-2017-05	HRMT36 – MultiMat	3	64	2	2
ARIES-HiRadMat-2018-01	HRMT43 – BeGrid2	8	640	4	3
ARIES-HiRadMat-2020-01	HRMT55 – BLM3	1	310	1	1
ARIES-HiRadMat-2021-01	HRMT56 - HED	7	200	3	2
ARIES-HiRadMat-2021-02	HRMT60 – RaDIATE2022	0*	0*	0*	0*
ARIES-HiRadMat-2021-03	HRMT57 – MultiMat2	1	50	1	1
ARIES-HiRadMat-2021-04	HRMT54 – EOBPM	1	60	1	1
ARIES-HiRadMat-2021-05	FIREBALL	2	150	2	2
Total:	12 projects	41 (different) users	2426	18 (different) institutes	11 (different) countries

*: due to COVID19-related travel restrictions imposed by the user's home institute no access units could be provided.

Table 2: List of TA projects at UNILAC M-Branch.

TA Project Acronym	Experiment	No. of Users	Access Units	No. of Institutes	No. of Countries
ARIES-GSI-M-BRANCH 2018-01	Ion-induced outgassing and sputtering of volatile and frozen gases	10	456	4	1

ARIES-GSI-M-BRANCH 2018-02	Radiation damage scaling in accelerator materials for beam intercepting devices: from high-flux light ions to high-energy protons	11	248	3	3
ARIES-GSI-M-BRANCH 2019-01	Heavy-ion induced effects on silicon carbide power MOSFETs	4	96	3	2
ARIES-GSI-M-BRANCH 2020-01	Radiation Hardness of Carbide and Nitride Compounds	9	144	3	2
Total:	4 Projects	33	944	13	7

3. Highlights of TA results

3.1. HiRADMAT

Throughout the 60-month duration of the project, an extensive list of experiments was conducted and supported by TA. In this section, a few highlights of experiments will be mentioned and briefly presented, along with a list of publications, as highlights of the TA results of the activities of WP10.1.

Experiments presented below in more detail:

Year	Experiment	Principle Investigator
2015	HRMT19 – BLM2	V. Grishin
2017	HRMT36 – MultiMat	A. Bertarelli
2018	HRMT47 – ATLASPixRad	A. Sbrizzi
2018	HRMT43 – BeGrid2	M. Calviani
2021	HRMT54 – EO BPM	T. Lefevre
2021	HRMT56 – HED	F.-X. Nuiiry

HRMT19 – BLM2

In this project, different types of Beam Loss Monitors (BLMs) were tested and compared. The signal linearity and response, calibration and saturation of the BLMs were studied. The project started in 2015 and benefited from TA support throughout 2017 and 2018. It received dedicated and parasitic beam time during 2018 and gained important data for the performance and the design of BLMs. The visiting team consisted of 3 members from the European Spallation Source ERIC (Lund, Sweden). Successful calibration of different ionization chambers was achieved. Tests confirmed the necessary design that will be produced for future installations at CERN, ESS and GSI/FAIR. Experimental results were published in 2 publications.

HRMT36 – MultiMat

The MultiMat experiment studied multiple currently used and novel material samples for beam-intercepting devices of the High-Luminosity upgrade of LHC (HL-LHC). The experiment was designed to test a large array of material specimens (e.g., graphitic materials, carbides and carbon-based composites and metal alloys) that are candidate materials for the novel HL-LHC collimators. The materials were tested with high intensity, high energy pulses, utilising the maximum proton pulse and smallest beam size offered by HiRadMat at the time (288 bunches at $\sim 3.5 \times 10^{13}$ protons per pulse with 0.25 mm beam sigma) to simulate conditions comparable to HL-LHC. The visiting team consisted of 3 members from the University of Malta (Malta) and Brevetti Bizz Srl (Italy). The experiment results on the response of the tested materials under beam impact aided the material qualification for the HL-LHC collimators and led to 6 peer-reviewed publications.

HRMT47 – ATLASPixRad

The goal of this experiment was to provide an estimate of the damage threshold of the ATLAS inner detectors and electronics under intense proton beam irradiation. ATLASPixRad was a continuation of HRMT41, that also benefited from TA support. The experimental set-up contained 3 Pixel modules, 2 ITk strip and 2 SCT strip modules and was exposed to gradually increasing beam intensities. Post Irradiation Examination was performed on all the modules to quantify the beam-induced damage on the modules. The visiting team consisted of 3 members from INFN Genova (Italy). The experiment successfully determined the damage threshold of the ATLAS tracker modules to approximately 10^{13} MIPS/cm². The experiment has provided valuable information regarding the application of these detectors in future HL-LHC beam loss scenarios. Results of these studies have been published in 4 peer-reviewed articles in various journals.

HRMT43 – BeGrid2

This was the first experiment in HiRadMat that involved the irradiation of pre-irradiated samples. The experiment was designed to investigate the thermal shock response of materials used for beam-intercepting devices and secondary particle production targets under the influence of radiation damage. Building on the experience of the previous HRMT24 – BeGrid experiment to expose specimens to even higher beam intensities and thermal shock conditions. Conventional (e.g., beryllium, graphite, silicon, glassy carbon and titanium alloys) and novel (e.g., electro-spun materials, metal foams) material specimens in pristine and proton pre-irradiated state were tested. The primary goal was to understand failure mechanisms, limits and flow behaviour of the material specimens and to compare and contrast the thermal shock responses of previously irradiated materials to their non-irradiated counterparts. The experimental set-up comprised of multiple arrays of specimens, each exposed to different beam intensities. Online diagnostics were performed (strain/temperature gauges, LDV system, and camera systems) to monitor the experiment in real-time. Post irradiation examination involved measuring out-of-plane permanent plastic deformation of the specimens with a profilometer, as well as advanced microscopic imaging systems (SEM, EDS, EBSD) to analyse the microstructural evolution of the specimens. The visiting team consisted of 7 members from Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (UK), Fermilab (USA), UK Atomic Energy Authority, KEK (Japan) and Rutherford Appleton Laboratory/STFC (UK). Future publications are expected.

HRMT54 – EOBPM

The aim of the experiment was the testing of a new type of high-frequency Beam Position Monitor (BPM) technology that can measure the intra-bunch position of short proton bunches rotated by the crab cavities in HL-LHC. The Electro-Optic Beam Position Monitor (EO-BPM), based on the polarization modulation of electro-optic crystals exposed to the electrical field of passing proton bunches, was tested using high intensity protons to study the transverse resolution performance of this technology. The conducted measurements involved pick-up sensitivity, bunch length and shape,

as well as the beam position sensitivity. The experiment ran in parallel to other beam instrument tests. One member of the team, from Royal Holloway, University of London, received TNA. This project will produce important data on the new BPM technologies and the results will define the BPMs' future design baseline and use in the SPS, LHC and HL-LHC.

HRMT56 – HED

The project's scope was to study the impact of high energy proton beams on currently used and novel material samples for use in high energy accelerators dump cores (HED). Sets of dedicated targets were irradiated with high-intensity proton beams to study the existing design of the LHC dump and to anticipate the materials' behaviour during future operations. Materials characterization tests were also performed for the needs of the future HL-LHC dump design. Various beam extraction absorber materials were also irradiated in view of their future use with HL-LHC equivalent beams. Finally, a new design for the dump beam diluter in graphite and carbon/carbon was tested to assess its robustness for the Future Circular Collider (FCC-ee). Target temperatures and surface vibrations for the most important samples were monitored. The experimental results already provided important input to the qualification of low-density graphites for (continued) use in the (HL-)LHC beam dumps. The project team consisted of 7 members from Norwegian University of Science and Technology and SINTEF (Norway) and UGR Granada (Spain).

3.1. UNILAC M-BRANCH

Within the TA activities at GSI UNILAC M-Branch 4 projects were served over the entire ARIES duration. The user community is very broad focussing on high functional materials related to state-of-the-art accelerator challenges. Here, ARIES TA played an important role to open fundamental research capabilities, as GSI UNILAC M-Branch, to communities focusing on technical developments with extreme material requirements. Finally, four projects were established dealing with: a) vacuum challenges regarding material outgassing b) material hardness studies c) radiation hardness of electronics d) microstructural material modifications related to radiation damage.

Due to the great response during ARIES, the foreseen access time (768 units) was increased up to 944 units, so that all projects could be served. Due to the COVID-19 situation, some experiments needed to be performed via remote access with support of the local M-Branch team.

ARIES-GSI-M-BRANCH PROJECTS

ARIES-GSI-M-BRANCH 2018-01

Ion-induced outgassing and sputtering of volatile and frozen gases

The outgassing due to ion induced desorption is a severe intensity limitation in modern accelerators, especially when an ion beam impacts on a solid target. We have studied the impact on the desorption yield (number of particles removed by incident ion) for different surface treatments on samples of stainless steel, copper and tungsten.

We used a dedicated UHV setup at the M-Branch which allows a total and partial gas analysis, with beams of 4.8 MeV/u Ca¹⁹⁺ or Ca¹⁰⁺ ions.

We irradiated several Cu, SS (Stainless Steel) and W samples with different surface preparations such as chemical or mechanical attacks, e-beam conditioning, annealing to determine the best treatment for minimizing the ion-induced desorption yield.

We also focused our study on the preparation of surfaces without annealing since in some cases, heating may deteriorate the mechanical properties of some beamline elements like for the future S3/SPIRAL2 facility at GANIL.

We also investigated the cleaning of the surface by the beam itself (the so-called “scrubbing effect”) with long irradiation time (around 6 hours) in order to separate thermal outgassing from outgassing due to the beam.

Last but not least, thanks to a calibrated Residual Gas Analyser, the evolution of the partial pressures of released gas (CO₂, CO, H₂ or others) under irradiation have been obtained. Some final results are extracted by combining our measurements with calculations from the Molflow (by R. Kersevan, CERN) software.

The collaboration includes 10 members from INSP (France), GANIL (France), IJCLab (France) and the Material research group of GSI.

Talks have been given and posters have been presented. Future publication is expected.

ARIES-GSI-M-BRANCH 2018-02

Radiation damage scaling in accelerator materials for beam intercepting devices: from high-flux light ions to high-energy protons

The assessment and mitigation of long-term damage induced in materials for Beam Intercepting Devices in general and collimators in particular is a fundamental aspect in the design of these components, particularly for high power, high brightness particle accelerators like HL-LHC or FCC. In order to anticipate such effects ahead of the operation, at the earliest possible stage of design, it is customary to perform irradiation campaigns relying on high intensity fluxes of protons and/or ions at

much lower energies. The scaling of effects and results to the high-energy case is however very complex as many parameters affect the behaviour of irradiated materials.

In this experiment, we performed irradiation at the M-Branch of UNILAC with Calcium ions on a range of materials used, or likely to be used, in collimators and beam intercepting devices, such as graphite-based ceramic composites and diamond-reinforced metals. Ions such as Carbon or Calcium are preferred since they are expected to generate radiation damage mostly by atomic displacement cascades, which can be compared to those induced by high-energy protons in the multi-TeV energy range. To this end, the experiment has been extensively simulated via particle interaction and transport codes (FLUKA), benchmarking the effects of irradiation runs against those expected in long-term accelerator operating conditions. Irradiated material samples have been examined and characterized, relying on offline facilities at GSI. The visiting team consisted of 11 members from 3 institutes.

ARIES-GSI-M-BRANCH 2019-01

Heavy-ion induced effects on silicon carbide power MOSFETs

Two microbeam experiments were performed at GSI-UNILAC in Darmstadt (Germany) using Ca and Au ions. The main objective was to study the single event effects in silicon carbide (SiC) power MOSFETs, a promising technology for space and high-energy-accelerator applications. The experiments focused on the single event leakage current (SELC) mechanism, which is characterized by a slow and permanent degradation of the drain and gate leakage currents with increasing heavy-ion fluence. This effect is unique for SiC technology and it is not observed in silicon power MOSFETs. This damage is not catastrophic, but the device operation may be altered which complicates the assessment of radiation tolerance in these parts. Bare dies were selected as devices under test (DUTs), in order to directly expose the chip surface to the beam and allow sufficient penetration of the heavy ions through the sensitive active layers of the device. Two Keithley source measure units (SMUs) were used to bias the gate and the drain and measure the leakage currents. The study allowed to identify two mechanisms of SELC, involving different areas of the MOSFET structure depending on the drain-source bias during the irradiation.

The visiting team consisted of 4 members from CERN (Switzerland), the University of Jyväskylä (Finland) and the Advanced Power Semiconductor (APS) Laboratory at ETH Zurich.

The work was published in IEEE TNS: C. Martinella et al., "Heavy-Ion Microbeam Studies of Single-Event Leakage Current Mechanism in SiC VD-MOSFETs," in IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science, vol. 67, no. 7, pp. 1381-1389, July 2020, doi: 10.1109/TNS.2020.3002729.

ARIES-GSI-M-BRANCH 2020-01

Radiation Hardness of Carbide and Nitride Compounds

Materials in energy-related applications, including nuclear reactors and accelerators, are subject to extreme conditions including high temperatures, and intense energetic particle irradiation. Such exposure results in substantial microstructural evolution, characterized by defect accumulation and material degradation. These effects are key factors that limit next-generation energy technologies, and, therefore, it is essential to close the current knowledge gap in understanding the microstructural evolution related to radiation damage in materials used for nuclear reactors and accelerators. The aim of this project was to generate valuable experimental data that are vital to understanding how different carbide and nitride compounds will perform under irradiation conditions, and the information gained will assist in developing future strategies in order to mitigate radiation damage-induced degradation. The radiation response of oxides is well understood, but it remains unclear how carbides with enhanced hardness and thermal stability behave under intense swift heavy ion beams. Three team members from the University of Tennessee, USA (Professor and two graduate students) conducted a study using 950 MeV Au ions – from the GSI M-Branch – to irradiate CeO₂ and ZrC with a range of ion fluences. Initial post-irradiation characterization involved synchrotron-based X-ray diffraction experiments at the Advanced Photon Source (Argonne National Laboratory, USA). Unit-cell swelling data from these experiments reveal that oxides and carbides have a distinct defect accumulation behaviour when irradiated with swift heavy ions. Oxides are characterized by a typical single-impact mechanism that is expressed by a linear increase in defect accumulation at lower fluences until saturation is reached at higher fluences. In clear contrast, irradiated carbide samples showed a two-step swelling process that appear not to saturate within fluences tested in this beamtime. Further experiments are needed to understand this behaviour. Current plans are to irradiate large volumes of ZrC materials at GSI and perform neutron total scattering experiments at the Spallation Neutron Source (Oak Ridge National Laboratory, USA). The data obtained in this beamtime is vital for considering the use of actinide carbides as next-generation nuclear materials in advanced reactors. The visiting team consisted of 9 members from 3 institutes.

4. List of Publications

4.1. HiRadMat

HiRadMat Facility

TA Project Acronym	Publication Year	Authors	Title	References	Publication type	Peer reviewed	DOI	Open Access
ARIES-HiRadMat-2017-01	2017	Y. Kadi, A. Fabich, F. Harden	HiRadMat Facility Experimental Program	NUFACT2017	Presentation	No	No	Yes
ARIES-HiRadMat-2017-01	2018	F.Harden, Y.Kadi	HiRadMat Facility Overview		Presentation	No	No	Yes
ARIES-HiRadMat-2017-01	2018	V. Grishin <i>et al.</i>	BLM2 at HiRadMat		Presentation	No	No	Yes
ARIES-HiRadMat-2017-01	2018	V. Grishin <i>et al.</i>	A Family of Gas Ionization Chambers and SEM for Beam Loss Monitoring of LHC and Other Accelerators	RuPAC2018	Conference proceedings	Yes	Yes	Yes
ARIES-HiRadMat-2017-01	2018	F.Harden, Y.Kadi, N. Charitonidis	HiRadMat: A Unique Facility Testing Materials with High Power Pulsed Beam	HiRadMat User Day	presentation	No	Yes	Yes

ARIES-HiRadMat-2017-02	2018	F. Carra <i>et al.</i>	The HRMT21 - RotCol experiment	HiRadMat User Day	presentation	No	Yes	Yes
ARIES-HiRadMat-2017-03	2018	A. Lapertosa <i>et al.</i>	ATLAS PixRad experiment: 2017 results & 2018 plans	HiRadMat User Day	presentation	No	Yes	Yes
ARIES-HiRadMat-2017-04	2018	D. Schmitt	Impact response of high-performance carbon-based materials	1st Annual Meeting of the ARIES WP17	Masters Thesis	No	Yes	Yes
ARIES-HiRadMat-2017-04	2018	P. Simon, M. Tomut <i>et al.</i>	First results of FlexMat experiment at HiRadMat- response of target and beam dump materials to beam impact	ARIES, wp17 1st Annual meeting, Malta, 29.10.18	presentation	No	Yes	Yes
ARIES-HiRadMat-2017-05	2018	A. Bertarelli <i>et al.</i>	Dynamic testing and characterization of advanced materials in a new experiment at Cern Hirammat facility		Conference proceedings	Yes	Yes	Yes
ARIES-HiRadMat-2017-05	2018	M. Pasquali <i>et al.</i>	The HRMT-36 Experiment (MultiMat)	HiRadMat User Day	presentation	No	Yes	Yes
WP10.1	2019	F. Harden, A. Bouvard, N. Charitonidis 1, Y. Kadi	HiRadmat: A facility beyond the realms of materials testing	J. Phys. Conf. Series 1350 012162.	Conference proceedings	yes	doi:10.1088/1742-6596/1350/1/012162	yes

ARIES-HiRadMat-2017-05	2019	F. Carra et al.	Mechanical robustness of HL-LHC collimator designs1	IOP Conf. Series: Journal of Physics: Conf. Series 1350 012083	Conference proceedings	yes	doi:10.1088/1742-6596/1350/1/012083	yes
ARIES-HiRadMat-2017-05	2019	M. Pasquali et al.	Dynamic Response of Advanced Materials Impacted by Particle Beams: The MultiMat Experiment	Journal of Dynamic Behavior of Materials 5 266–95	Conference proceedings	yes	doi:10.1007/s40870-019-00210-1	yes
ARIES-HiRadMat-2017-05	2019	M. Portelli et al.	Numerical and experimental benchmarking of the dynamic response of SiC and TZM specimens in the MultiMat experiment	Mechanics of materials 138 103169	Conference proceedings	yes	doi:10.1016/j.mechmat.2019.103169	yes
ARIES-HiRadMat-2017-02	2019	T. Markiewicz et al.	Design, construction, and beam tests of a rotatable collimator prototype for high-intensity and high-energy hadron accelerators	Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams 22 123002.	Conference proceedings	yes	doi:10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.22.123002	yes
ARIES-HiRadMat-2017-03	2019	C. Bertella et al.	Test with high-energy and high-intensity proton beam on ATLAS silicon detectors towards HL-LHC	Nuovo Cim. C42 205	Conference proceedings	yes	doi:10.1393/ncc/i2019-19205-8	yes
ARIES-HiRadMat-2017-03	2019	C. Bertella et al.	Damages induced on ATLAS IBL modules by fast extracted and intense proton beam irradiation	JINST 14 C05024	Conference proceedings	yes	doi:10.1088/1748-0221/14/05/C05024	yes
ARIES-HiRadMat-2017-03	2019	J. Fernandez-Tejero et al.	Beam-loss damage experiment on ATLAS-like silicon strip modules using an intense proton beam	Nuclear Inst. And Methods in Physics Research A 958 162838	Conference proceedings	yes	doi:10.1016/j.nima.2019.162838	yes

HiRadMat Facility	2021	F. Harden et al.	Targetry Challenges & HiRadMat	Proceedings of the 3rd J-PARC Symposium (J-PARC2019).	Conference proceedings	Yes	10.7566/jpsc.33.011149	Yes
On-line instrumentation for HiRadMat Experiments	2021	F. Carra et al.	Design and Construction of an Instrumentation System to Capture the Response of Advanced Materials Impacted by Intense Proton Pulses	Shock and Vibration, Volume 2021 Article ID 8855582	Journal Publication	Yes	10.1155/2021/8855582	Yes
ARIES-CERN-HiRadMat-2017-01	2018	V. Grishin et al.	A Family of Gas Ionization Chambers and SEM for Beam Loss Monitoring of LHC and Other Accelerators	Proc. 26th Russian Particle Accelerator Conf. (RuPAC'18) 44-48	Journal Publication	Yes	10.18429/JACoW-RuPAC2018-TUZMH03	Yes
ARIES-CERN-HiRadMat-2017-05	2018	A. Bertarelli et al.	Dynamic testing and characterization of advanced materials in a new experiment at CERN HiRadMat facility	IOP Conf. Series: Journal of Physics: Conf. Series 1067 082021	Conference proceedings	Yes	10.1088/1742-6596/1067/8/082021	Yes
ARIES-CERN-HiRadMat-2017-05	2021	M Portelli et al.	Thermomechanical Characterisation of Copper Diamond and Benchmarking with the MultiMat Experiment	Shock and Vibration, Volume 2021 Article ID 8879400	Journal Publication	Yes	10.1155/2021/8879400	Yes
ARIES-CERN-	2021	P. Simon et al.	Dynamic response of graphitic targets with tantalum cores impacted by pulsed 440-GeV proton beams	Shock and Vibration Volume 2021 Article ID 8884447	Journal Publication	Yes	10.1155/2021/8884447	Yes

TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS TO MATERIAL TESTING FACILITIES

Deliverable: D10.1

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HiRadMat- 2017-04								
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Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
BID	Beam-intercepting device
BLM	Beam Loss Monitor
BPM	Beam Position Monitor
HL-LHC	High Luminosity Large Hadron Collider
PIE	Post Irradiation Examination
TA - TNA	Transnational Access